

The Project Method as a Means of Developing Students' Communicative Competencies in Russian Language Lessons

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Abstract: the article presents an analysis of the project technology method from the point of view of the optimality of its application to achieve the goals and objectives of teaching the Russian language at the present stage. The peculiarity of project activity is determined as one of the best ways of creative independent work of students.

Key words: project activity, teaching the Russian language, creative activity, joint work of teacher and student, innovative teaching, research activity, independent work.

Currently, in the domestic methodology of teaching foreign languages, there is an increased interest in the project-based methodology, which makes it possible to build learning on a personal-activity basis. Project activities are used as various components of the learning process: as a built-in component in various modules, as an independent module, as a technology for the entire learning process, through which approximately half of the curriculum is planned to be implemented in individual universities [1].

A project is understood as independently planned and implemented work in a foreign language, for example, the publication of a newspaper or magazine, a collection of articles, the preparation of an exhibition, performance, concert, report, etc. [2]. This is such independently planned and implemented work, in which “verbal communication is woven into the intellectual and emotional context of other activities” [3]. A.V. Konyshcheva examines the didactic typology of projects developed by E.S. Polat, and presents it in the form of a table [4].

In educational activities, the listed types of projects do not exist in their pure form, so we have to deal with mixed types of projects. However, any project has one or another type of coordination, deadlines and stages of execution, and a larger or smaller number of participants.

The methodology uses several terms that characterize the project and project activities: project method, project methodology, project-based learning technology, project-based learning, project-based (projective) education. I.A. Winter, T.E. Sakharov and after them A.V. Konyshcheva [4] define the project method as a way to achieve a didactic goal through a detailed development of the problem, which ends with a very real, tangible, practical result, formalized in one way or another. It allows you to integrate students' knowledge from different fields, makes it possible to apply it in practice when solving a given problem, and helps optimize the learning process.

Table 1. Didactic typology of projects

By type of activity	• Research, creative, role-playing, informational, practice-oriented
According to subject area	• Mono-projects, interdisciplinary projects
According to the nature of coordination	• A project with open, explicit coordination; projects with hidden coordination
By the nature of contacts	• Domestic, regional, international
By number of participants	• Personal, paired, group
According to the duration of the event	• Short term, medium duration; long-term

In our opinion, the essence of the project method lies in its interactive nature, since the project implies not only the interaction of the teacher and students, but also the cooperation and co-creation of the students themselves.

The terms “project-based learning technology” and “project methodology” are used interchangeably [5]. The project methodology is implemented in project-based learning, in which learning activities are carried out within the framework of projects of various types. Features of the design methodology are:

- stability of communication between stages of work,
- continuity,
- mobility and flexibility,
- mobility of boundaries between stages and their interpenetration [5].

The design methodology arose on the basis of the method proposed by T. Hutchinson. It was designed to teach teenagers for three years and provided for the organization of communicative-cognitive activities in a foreign language lesson in the form of a project, during the implementation of which problematic tasks are solved, searches are carried out and involuntary memorization of lexical units and grammatical structures occurs [6].

E.S. Polat considers the project methodology as a set of search, problem-based methods, creative in their very essence, representing a didactic means of enhancing cognitive activity, developing creativity and forming certain personal qualities of students in the process of creating a specific product [7].

It should be noted that currently the project methodology is widely used in the higher education system. When teaching foreign languages, including the Russian language, it opens up wide opportunities for the formation of both foreign language communicative competence and a number of components of general competencies, such as: the ability to work independently, the ability to find and analyze information, the ability to identify problems in the course of educational activities and solve them, self-confidence and the ability to take responsibility, the ability to apply knowledge in practice, mastery of information technology, the ability to self-educate.

When teaching foreign languages, project-based methodology is implemented in various forms, some of which have been used traditionally. These include preparing reports, organizing evenings and exhibitions in a foreign language.

Currently, when developing university project methodology, special attention is paid to group project-based learning through the implementation of research creative group projects. Such projects involve “the embodiment of innovative ideas and proposals that can be implemented in the form of creating new high-tech products and technologies that are in demand in the market or industry” [1].

The term “projective education” appeared in the conditions of innovative development of industry and the economy and the need for changes in the technologies of higher technical education. Project-based education implies an education that not only creates conditions for providing enterprises with highly qualified specialists, but also directly participates in the development and responsible implementation of innovative projects. Its distinctive feature is “the integration of educational learning processes (self-learning) and activity-based innovative design with elements of advanced education.” In this case, according to a number of authors, the project is used both as a teaching technology and as “a means of creating and implementing a project that has a life and not just educational meaning for the student” [8].

Project-based (project-based) education provides for the active participation of students in working on real production modernization projects and in the implementation of collective strategic innovative programs for the development of industrial enterprises [8]. Considering the range of use of projects in teaching Russian as a foreign language at a university, it should be noted that the project method has been widely used and is currently used as a built-in component in various modules.

Teaching the Russian language at the Tashkent University of Applied Sciences is carried out within the framework of a multi-level, five-component, personality-oriented, professional-activity test-oriented system of teaching foreign languages at the university [9]. One of the most important components of the Russian as a foreign language teaching system is the methodological system. A person-oriented methodological system creates the conditions necessary for Uzbek Tashkent University of Applied Sciences students to realize their goals, needs, abilities and capabilities through teaching Russian as a foreign language. It opens up wide possibilities for using project methodology in the course of the Russian as a foreign language not only in the form of traditional educational projects, but also in its innovative forms. The emergence of innovative forms and types of educational project activities is associated with the introduction of information technologies into the educational process. The use of various types of computer activities and their inclusion in project activities has significantly changed the latter, filled it with new content, and expanded its educational, educational and developmental components.

Today, work on an educational project when studying Russian as a foreign language involves not only the establishment of interdisciplinary connections and integration of different academic disciplines, but also opens up the possibility of students implementing educational and professional activities within the framework of the project. We consider it possible to use the project as a component of the process of teaching the grammatical aspect of Russian as a foreign language and conduct project-based training in project groups of first-year students studying in different specialties.

Project-based learning is carried out within one or two modules, depending on the topic of the project, and assumes a high level of foreign language communicative skills and a sufficient level of professional competencies of students participating in the project. It is based on the principle of concentricism, which is considered as a methodological principle of teaching and involves expanding the material in subsequent concentration based on what has been learned and mastering new things [2].

A practical course of the Russian language as an academic discipline is fertile ground for project-based teaching technology. We, teachers, often encounter problems such as lack of reading interest among students, narrow horizons, lack of analysis and generalization skills. Interesting work in groups gives students the opportunity to get a feel for the subject, gain new knowledge, and the teacher to solve the above problems.

Offering such tasks as making a selection of proverbs on a certain topic, compiling a catalog of these proverbs in certain sections, compiling a dictionary of phraseological units, students are given the opportunity to obtain the necessary information from different sources, communicate with other participants in the mini-project, outline an action plan, and fantasize about how will work out, and then compare with what happened.

It is important in educational activities to give each student the opportunity to feel involved in the world, to come into contact with their own creativity, to find the reader and viewer within themselves, and such forms as mini-essays, dramatization, making crossword puzzles, drawing illustrations, etc. help in solving this problem. .

Mandatory conditions for this are a clear definition of the completion of the task in time and reflection on the activity, i.e. assessment of what each person personally gained from completing this or that educational task, what was successful and what was not, what were the reasons for failure and how to avoid this in the future. It is important that in such reflection, students learn to adequately evaluate themselves and discuss the results of their activities.

In order for students to develop cooperation skills and involve them in the active process of obtaining information processing, it is necessary to organize interaction, which includes connections “student-student”, “student-teacher”, “teacher-student”, “student-group”, with the help methods that focus attention on a large group: survey, discussion, dispute, review of information, dramatization, discussions. You can create a problem-motivational environment in the lesson in different forms: conversation, discussion, brainstorming, independent work, organizing a round table, consultation, seminar, group work, role-playing games. And also let you complete more complex projects: create visual aids, write informational abstracts, research papers.

The purpose of project technology in the Russian language lesson is to develop the creative potential of students. Students learn to use knowledge to solve cognitive and practical problems; working in creative groups and individually, acquire communication skills; By becoming researchers, they learn to identify problems. Collect the necessary information, observe, analyze, build hypotheses, draw conclusions and generalizations. In the process of working on the project, students' systems thinking develops. When using the project method in the Russian language lesson, one should strive to increase the practical orientation of the content, diversify the forms of organizing students' educational activities, self-education, which provides conditions for the realization of students' creative potential.

By creating game situations in Russian language lessons, you can develop attention, intelligence, a sense of competition, mutual assistance, and introduce variety and emotional release. Making teaching aids and composing crossword puzzles on a topic is the ability to put your knowledge into practice, think about and create a new product - your project. By intelligently and appropriately using this type of activity along with traditional forms, the teacher captivates students and thereby creates the basis for a better perception of large and complex material.

REFERENCES

1. Кенжабоев, А. Э. & Кенжабоев, Ж. А. (2017). Умумтаълим мактаблари ўқитувчиларида касбий компетентликни шакллантиришнинг илмий-педагогик асослари. *Современное образование (Узбекистан)*, (11), 22-26.
2. Кенжабоев, Ж. А. & Кучкинов, Х. Х. (2017). САМОСТОЯТЕЛЬНАЯ РАБОТА УЧАЩИХСЯ НА УРОКАХ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА. *Вопросы педагогики*, (9), 33-35.
3. Kenjabayev, J. A. Linguistic features of the development of oral speech competence of students of the direction of physical culture education (on the example of sports terminology). *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences.-UK*, 11, 48-51.
4. Соляхова, Л. Р. (2021). Использование Инновационных Методов При Развитии Потенциала Обучению Английского Языка У Курсантов Академии Вооруженных Сил Республики Узбекистан. *Oriental Renaissance: Innovative, Educational, Natural And Social Sciences*, 1(11), 1166-1171.
5. Кенжабаев, Ж. (2022). The implementation of literature in teaching speaking for advanced students. *Общество и инновации*, 3(2/S), 262-265.
6. Кенжабаев, Ж. (2023). СОВРЕМЕННЫЙ ЭТАП РАЗВИТИЯ НАУКИ О ЯЗЫКЕ. *Экономика и социум*, (2 (105)), 704-707.
7. Кенжабоев, А. & Кенжабоев, Ж. (2015). Тарбия технологияси ва унинг долзарблиги. *Современное образование (Узбекистан)*, (4), 61-64.
8. Кенжабоев, А. Э. & Кенжабоев, Ж. А. (2016). ХОРИЖИЙ ТИЛЛАРНИ ЎРГАТИШДА ПЕДАГОГИК ТЕХНОЛОГИЯЛАР. *Ученый XXI века*, (3-2 (16)), 44-49.
9. Кенжабоев, Ж. А. (2017). Психолого-педагогические аспекты формирования диалога как компонента иноязычного обучения. *Вестник современной науки*, (3-2), 48-50.
10. Nigora, S. (2021). On The Manuscript Copies of “Al Kashshof” By Makhmud Zamakhshari. *Turkish Journal of Computer and Mathematics Education (TURCOMAT)*, 12(7), 2032-2042.
11. Sulaymonova, N. A. (2020). The Work “Al-Mufasssal Fi San’ati-L-I’rob” By Mahmud Zamakhshari and Its Lithography Copies. *The American Journal of Applied sciences*, 2(09), 17-24.
12. Sulaymonova, N., & Sulaymonova, K. (2015). A GREAT SCIENTIST OF KHOREZM. *International Journal*, (1).
13. Сулаймонова, Н. & Сулаймонова, К. (2015). Фразеологизмы в произведении Махмуда Замахшари «асо-л-балого». *Восточный факел*, 1(1), 21-24.
14. Sulaymanova, N. (2019). CONFIDENTIAL REVIEW AT LITERARY HERITAGE OF MAHMUD ZAMAKHSHARIY. *European Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, (6), 162-166.
15. SULAYMONOVA, N., & SULAYMANOVA, K. ZAMAKHSHARIY“ S SCIENTIFIC ACTIVITY. *MATER I ALLARI*, 491.
16. Toxirovna, K. F. (2021). LIFELONG LEARNING–LLL–THE BASIS OF PERSONAL DEVELOPMENT. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(8), 119-123.
17. Tohirova, K. F. (2021, February). Bologna Treaty and ECTS (EUROPEAN CREDIT TRANSFER SYSTEM). In *Archive of Conferences* (Vol. 14, No. 1, pp. 25-31).
18. Хусаинова, Ф. Т. (2020). ТАШКЕНТ В ПРОШЛОМ–В ЦЕННОМ ПИСЬМЕННОМ НАСЛЕДИИ «ТАРИХИ ЖАДИДАЙИ ТОШКАНД». *Review of law sciences*, (1), 183-187.

19. Khusainova, F. (2020). Ancestral heritage is a priceless treasure. Human and its spiritual problems in Avesto. *Oriental Art and Culture*, (I (2)), 135-137.
20. Yashnarovna, A. A. M. (2021, November). Intelligent Management Model Of Business Processes Of Production With The Use Of Fuzzy Logic Apparatus. In *2021 International Conference on Information Science and Communications Technologies (ICISCT)* (pp. 1-3). IEEE.
21. Abdul-Azalova, M. Y., & Mamatova, N. M. (2021). Big data technologies in technological and business processes automatization. *Big Data and Advanced Analytics*, (7-1), 50-58.
22. Muhamediyeva, D., & Abdul-Azalova, M. (2022). Application of the theory of fuzzy logic for analysis of management systems of business processes of an enterprise. *Scientific Collection «InterConf+»*, (22 (113)), 467-471.
23. Mengliyev, B. (2022). PEDAGOGICAL COMPETENCE OF A MODERN PHYSICAL EDUCATION TEACHER. *Science and innovation*, 1(B7), 554-556.
24. Sagdullayevna, K. V. (2022). YOSH GIMNASTIKACHILARNING MAXSUS TAYYORGARLIK BOSQICHIDAGI FAOLIYATINING MAZMUNI VA USLUBIYATI. *International Journal of Philosophical Studies and Social Sciences*, 110-113.
25. Менглиев, Б. Н. & Умиров, Ш. Б. (2020). ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ ВНЕДРЕНИЯ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ НА ЗАНЯТИЯХ ФИЗИЧЕСКОЙ КУЛЬТУРОЙ. In *ИННОВАЦИОННОЕ РАЗВИТИЕ: ПОТЕНЦИАЛ НАУКИ И СОВРЕМЕННОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ* (pp. 119-121).
26. Ixtiyorovich, N. N., & Abdurashidovich, U. A. (2022). Study the Location of the Useful Component from the Tailings of the Gold Recovery Plant. *International Journal of Innovative Analyses and Emerging Technology*, 2(1), 5-8.
27. Khayitov, O. G. O., Ziyodov, N. R., Fatkhiddinov, A. O. T. O., & Umirzoqov, A. A. (2021). THE INTENSITY OF THE EFFECT OF THE EXPLOSION OF BOREHOLE CHARGES OF EXPLOSIVES IN MULTI-STRENGTH ROCKS OF DEEP QUARRIES. *Scientific progress*, 2(1), 625-630.
28. Бабаев, З. Н., Умирзоков, А. А., & Петросов, Ю. Э. (2020). Технично-экономическое обоснование кондиций для подсчета запасов горючих сланцев месторождения сангунтау. *Студенческий вестник*, (10-2), 18-20.
29. Хайитов, О., Джураев, С., Умирзоков, А., Бекманов, Н., & Искандаров, Ж. (2021). НЕКОТОРЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ РЕЗУЛЬТАТОВ ВСКРЫТИЯ, ИСПЫТАНИЯ И ОСВОЕНИЯ ПОИСКОВО-РАЗВЕДОЧНЫХ СКВАЖИН. *Збірник наукових праць SCIENTIA*.
30. Nasirov, U., Umirzoqov, A., & Fathiddinov, A. (2021). ANALYSIS OF THE MODERN DEVELOPMENT OF MINING AND PROCESSING COMPLEXES IN UZBEKISTAN. *Збірник наукових праць ЛОГОΣ*.
31. Ochilov, S. H. (2017). A., Umirzoqov AA, Determining the optimal distance between parallel-converged borehole charges when blasting high ledges. *Bulletin TSTU–Tashkent*, 3, 167-174.
32. Usmanovich, S. A., Ikhtiyorovich, N. N., & Abdurashidovich, U. A. (2022). Processing of Layout Tails of Gold-Extracting Plants. *Central Asian Journal of Theoretical and Applied Science*, 3(1), 7-13.
33. Петросов, Ю., Хайитов, О., Умирзоков, А., Исаманов, У., & Имамбердиев, Ў. (2021). ПРОБЛЕМЫ ДОБЫЧИ И ПЕРЕРАБОТКИ ПОЛЕЗНЫХ ИСКОПАЕМЫХ В УСЛОВИЯХ ГЛУБОКИХ КАРЬЕРОВ. *Збірник наукових праць SCIENTIA*.
34. Samadov, A. U., Nosirov, N. I., & Umirzoqov, A. A. (2022). Overview of the concepts of gold recovery from stale tailings of a gold recovery plant. *BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 2(1), 3-8.

35. Umirzoqov, A. (2020). The Tasks of Optimal Design and Research of Systems for Cleaning Gas Emissions of Industrial Enterprises. *International Journal of Engineering and Information Systems (IJEAIS) ISSN*.
36. G'ofurovich, K. O., & Abdurashidovich, U. A. (2021). Justification of rational parameters of transshipment points from automobile conveyor to railway transport. *World Economics and Finance Bulletin*, 1(1), 20-25.